

New taxa of *Parexarnis* Boursin, 1946 from Asia (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae, Noctuinae)

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Abstract. Three new *Parexarnis* Boursin, 1946 species, and five new *Parexarnis* subspecies are described. The main external and genitalia features of the new species and their closest relatives are characterised and discussed. The images are illustrated on five tables with 40 colour figures, the genitalia are presented on seven monochromatic plates with figures of 18 males and 14 females.

Keywords. *Parexarnis*, Asia, new species, new subspecies, description, taxonomy.

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Introduction

Parexarnis Boursin, 1946 is one of the taxonomically most difficult genera of Noctuidae with 21 described species. In a few taxonomical publications (Fibiger & Lafontaine, 2005; Fibiger & Lafontaine, 2005 (2.); Skule, B. & Nilsson, D. 2008; Fibiger et al., 2010, [https://ftp.funet.fi/index/Tree of life/ insecta/lepidoptera /ditrysia/noctuoidea/noct-uidae/noctuinae/actebia/](https://ftp.funet.fi/index/Tree%20of%20life/insecta/lepidoptera/ditrysia/noctuoidea/noct-uidae/noctuinae/actebia/), etc.), it is downgraded into the genus *Actebia* Stephens, 1829 as a subgenus of it, with the following close relative genera: *Perissandria* Warren, 1909, *Protexarnis* McDunnough, [1929], *Hemiexarnis* Boursin, 1948, *Ledereragrotis* Varga, 1990. The author of this publication cannot accept this concept, and he still considers *Parexarnis* and the genera mentioned above as valid, distinct genera, as in some other publications, e.g. Hreblay, Ronkay & Plante (1998), Aulombard et al., 2020, since those have well defined different external and genitalia characters.

Parexarnis is exclusively Palearctic, relatively rich in species, having a wide distributional range from western Europe and northern Africa through Anatolia, the Near East, Caucasus, Central- and Inner Asia, to the Himalayas and Tibetan plateau. The most diverse is in the high mountains in the Central- and Inner Asian high mountains. In the case of some species, there is a great individual variability in the external characters, and sometimes even in the shape of some of the characters of the genitalia. This may be why the various literatures do not agree even in the eastern limits of the distribution of the well-known *P. fugax* (Treitschke, 1825).

Rhyacia dormitans Corti & Draudt, 1933 (TL: Kuku-noor, Qinghai) is very similar to *P. l. laetifica* by its external features, figured in Seitz Supplement, 1938; can be a subspecies or form of it. [https://ftp.funet.fi/index of Actebia](https://ftp.funet.fi/index%20of%20Actebia) synonymised it to *P. l. laetifica*. Hreblay, Ronkay & Plante (1998, pp 123) suspected it as a synonym of *Parexarnis obumbrata* (Staudinger, 1889). The genitalia of *dormitans* were not available. Author dissected a male and female specimen from an externally resembling series from the type locality of *dormitans*, however both proved to be *P. poecila* (Alphéraky, 1888).

Hacker (1990) considered *P. pseudosollers* (Boursin, 1940), *P. taurica* (Staudinger, 1889), and *P. damnata* (Draudt, 1937) to be three different species. Hreblay, Ronkay & Plante (1998, p. 123) in their list of *Parexarnis*, synonymized *P. pseudosollers* to *P. taurica*, while *P. damna-*